

CONSTRUCTION AND ARCHITECTURE

OPTIMIZATION OF QUALITY CONTROL METHODS IN CONSTRUCTION: INNOVATIVE APPROACHES AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract

This article analyzes modern quality control methods in the construction industry aimed at improving the reliability, safety, and durability of constructed facilities. It examines innovative approaches, including the use of robotic systems, drones, and various digital technologies. Optimization methods such as standardization, process automation, predictive analytics, and non-destructive testing are explored. The article emphasizes the importance of implementing these technologies to optimize all stages of construction, increase productivity, and reduce risks.

Keywords: quality control, construction industry, optimization, standardization, automation, predictive analytics, robotic systems, digital technologies.

Introduction

Quality control in the construction industry is one of the most essential processes directly affecting the reliability, safety, and durability of structures. A high level of quality reduces the risk of accidents and helps avoid costly rework. It becomes especially significant in complex and long-term construction projects. Therefore, the process itself must be as precise, consistent, and comprehensive as possible to ensure that structures meet strict standards and requirements.

For many years, traditional control methods have been used in construction, including visual inspections and laboratory material testing. These methods played a foundational role in establishing quality systems, but as structures become more complex and project timelines more demanding, there is a growing need for modernized approaches. Implementing contemporary quality standards requires companies to adopt more flexible and comprehensive control tools that can respond to deviations in the early stages of construction and quickly address potential defects.

As the scale and complexity of construction projects increase, so does the need for new methods to improve control processes. Among these methods are the use of digital solutions, sensor systems, and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, which enable high-precision data collection and analysis. These innovations

are designed to enhance quality control efficiency, optimize costs, and minimize errors. The aim of this study is to explore modern quality control methods in the construction sector and evaluate their effectiveness.

Main part. Innovative approaches in quality control methods

Modern construction becomes an increasingly complex and multilayered process, involving multiple stages and participants. In this context, quality control is one of the key elements that ensures structures meet standards of safety, durability, and functionality. With the rapid development of technology, construction companies are increasingly adopting innovative approaches that optimize quality control and construction processes [1].

Building Information Modeling (BIM) technology enables data management related to construction projects in a digital model format. The use of BIM at all stages of construction allows for quality control of the project based on comprehensive and up-to-date information. A primary advantage of BIM is the ability to predict potential errors and discrepancies even at the design stage. Among other benefits, the tool also enables the automation of control and reporting processes, simplifying the identification and correction of errors (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Worldwide survey results on optimization of BIM processes in corporate settings in the construction sector, 2022, % [2]

The system enables the prediction of potential errors and inconsistencies as early as the design phase,

making this innovation an important element in creating a transparent, integrated approach to quality management throughout the entire project lifecycle.

The integration of **sensor systems** and **Internet of Things (IoT)** technologies in the construction industry opens new possibilities for quality control. These tools allow for real-time data collection and analysis regarding the condition of the site. Sensors installed at various stages of construction gather information about parameters that affect the quality and safety of structures. Furthermore, it can identify building materials with a high accuracy of 82,75%, which increases to 83,07% when combined with remote sensing data from technologies like LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) [3]. Modern IoT systems consolidate this data and provide a comprehensive view of the process. The integration of IoT with BIM creates opportunities to build digital twins, providing a complete real-time view of the condition of the construction site.

The integration of **drones (UAV, unmanned aerial vehicles)** into construction processes has become

one of the most effective innovations in quality control [4]. They provide precise visual data that is difficult to collect using traditional methods, enabling more comprehensive monitoring of construction sites. Drones can conduct regular inspections of construction sites to assess their current state and track progress. These devices can capture images from different angles and heights, covering the entire site and identifying areas requiring special attention. Drones also enable inspections in hard-to-reach and hazardous areas of construction sites.

These devices also help detect defects and potential issues at early stages, reducing the likelihood of costly rework and delays. Equipped with high-quality cameras and thermal imaging sensors, drones can identify cracks, corrosion, leaks, and other defects in structures, as well as perform thermal inspections to detect areas with heat loss or potential insulation issues. Modern UAV in construction are equipped with advanced technologies that enable precise assessment of structural quality (table 1).

Table 1.

Characteristics of components of modern UAV used in the construction industry [5]

Technology needs/components	Description
Vehicle type: rotary-wing	Composed of one or multiple propellers. Do not require runways, as they can take-off and land vertically. High hovering capabilities. Considered safe and stable due to propellers redundancy. Low flying endurance.
Flying style: autonomous flights characteristics used	Auto-Return Home. Auto take-off/landing. Obstacle avoidance. Way-point navigation. Guarded motion. Follow target.
Onboard sensors	Visual cameras. Thermal cameras. Motion detection. LiDAR. Audio sensors. RFID readers. Air quality sensors.

With technological advancements, the construction industry is actively adopting **robotics** and **automation** to enhance accuracy and efficiency in tasks. These systems help execute labor-intensive and repetitive tasks with minimal human involvement, thus reducing costs and improving quality control. A primary area of robotics is the use of specialized construction robots capable of performing repetitive tasks at high speed and precision. An example is brick and block laying, where specialized robots like SAM100 (Semi-Automated Mason) can lay bricks with speed and precision that far exceed human capabilities [6]. Robots can pour concrete and smooth surfaces, ensuring uniformity and quality of finishes. They are equipped with cameras and sensors that enable automated inspection of structures for defects and deviations from project standards.

Augmented Reality (AR) technologies enable the overlay of a project's 3D model onto the physical structure. It allows for a direct comparison between the planned design and the actual state on the construction site. Workers can visually assess how the completed structure should appear and identify any discrepancies with the project in real time. By viewing the projected model directly on-site, they gain immediate insights into alignment, positioning, and design accuracy. This tool assists workers in monitoring the precision of their work and adjusting deviations as they occur. These systems can be specifically valuable in complex engineering tasks. With AR, construction teams can verify that each component is correctly positioned, as it ensures

that the project aligns with specifications down to the finest details.

Innovative approaches, such as drones, BIM, IoT, and robotics, contribute to the optimization of quality control methods in construction. Integrating these technologies allows construction companies to achieve high quality standards, reduce costs, and minimize human error.

Optimization of the quality control process

Quality control in construction encompasses multiple stages, from verifying project documentation to inspecting finished structures. With increasing demands for quality and efficiency in construction processes, optimizing quality control has become a priority for companies aiming to minimize errors, enhance reliability, and reduce costs.

One of the initial steps toward optimizing quality control is the **standardization** of all stages in the construction process. Using standardized checklists and guidelines ensures a consistent approach to inspections and quality checks at all levels. This method also helps reduce the number of errors and omissions during quality assessments by applying a structured approach. Standardizing processes facilitates the identification of causes for defects and deviations, as the sequence of actions affecting quality can be easily traced. The gradual implementation of standardized procedures enables companies to maintain consistent high standards across all their projects.

Digitalization and **automation** are key elements of optimization that make quality control more efficient and precise. Automation systems help minimize human involvement in inspections, reducing the likelihood of errors and enhancing real-time monitoring. The advantages of automation include automated data collection and analysis. Digital platforms and sensor systems allow for real-time gathering of information about the site's condition and quality parameters, thus accelerating the decision-making process.

One of the advanced technologies in quality control optimization is **predictive analytics**, which uses data analysis from previous projects to forecast potential issues at the current construction stage. By identifying patterns and correlations within large data sets, predictive analytics can help construction teams anticipate structural weaknesses, material failures, and scheduling delays before they arise, allowing for a more proactive approach to project management.

The application of **AI** and **machine learning** enables the detection of hidden dependencies and risk factors that may go unnoticed with traditional quality control methods [7]. These algorithms can learn from historical project data and sensor feedback, continuously improving their accuracy in predicting issues as more data becomes available. This process improves risk assessment and enables dynamic adjustments to construction workflows based on real-time feedback.

Non-destructive testing (NDT) methods allow for the inspection of construction materials and structures without causing damage, significantly improving the quality control process. Key NDT methods include ultrasonic testing, radiographic testing, and magnetic testing. These technologies enable the assessment of material strength and quality at every stage of construction [8]. Ultrasonic testing uses high-frequency sound waves to detect internal flaws, such as cracks or voids, within concrete or metal elements, providing precise data on material thickness and consistency. Radiographic testing, employing X-rays or gamma rays, reveals hidden defects by capturing detailed internal images of materials. It is commonly applied for inspecting welds and joints. Magnetic particle testing is particularly effective for ferromagnetic materials, where magnetic fields highlight surface and near-surface flaws that may otherwise be overlooked.

Optimizing the quality control process requires a comprehensive approach that includes process standardization, automation, and the use of advanced technologies for monitoring and data analysis. These meth-

ods enhance the accuracy and efficiency of quality control, making the construction process more economically viable and safer for all participants.

Conclusion

Innovative methods and optimization of quality control processes have become key elements of successful construction projects. The adoption of new technologies, such as drones, sensor systems, and automated platforms, enhances the accuracy and responsiveness of control, reducing costs and minimizing human error. Process standardization, task automation, and improved coordination among project participants facilitate smoother workflows and ensure adherence to high-quality standards. The use of predictive analytics and non-destructive testing helps anticipate and prevent defects. This approach makes the construction process safer, more reliable, and economically efficient.

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